

D7.4

Serious game

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D7.4/Serious game

Lead by Arctik

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Abstract

“Bridging the Silos” is a game designed by Marleen de Ruiter, Anaïs Couasnon, and Philip Ward at the [Institute for Environmental Studies of the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam](#). It was originally developed as a tabletop board game, and then further adapted to a web-based version by Justin Daneau, with input from Marleen de Ruiter and Nicole van Maanen. For an in-depth description of the tabletop version, [see the original paper](#). Although the serious game (D7.4) released on the MYRIAD-EU dashboard differs in design and features from the original game, the core purpose remains the same: giving the opportunity to keen climate researchers, policymakers, and civil society to **move past a “silo mentality”** and reinforce cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration to inform a better hazard response.

Designed for both expert and general audiences, it ultimately serves as a tool to educate about a multi-hazard DRR perspective. By adopting a role play approach, the game encourages players to familiarise with the concept of multi-hazard disaster risk reduction (DRR), implement so-called “measures” which help to either mitigate or prevent damage caused by natural hazards, and witness firsthand the challenges of decision-making in a changing climate. The game focuses on three of these natural hazards: **floods, tropical cyclones, and droughts**. Players can choose among eight roles: **president, finance minister, engineer, national flood coordinator, agricultural representative, citizen representative, national housing chief, international aid representative**. These are then plunged into fictitious yet plausible multi-risk scenarios where they are encouraged to discuss in multiple rounds, discuss their views, and finally reach a consensus on how to deploy aid and money. All in all, the game invites users to take on different stakeholder roles and explore strategies and tools for managing complex, interconnected risks. A storyboard was initially created to structure scenarios and choices, which was refined through input from stakeholders during a beta testing phase.

The first usability testing session for the MYRIAD-EU serious game ‘Bridging the Silos’ was held on **Monday, 2 December 2024**. Overall, this trial run revealed several gameplay-related challenges. One major issue encountered was that switching to other browser tabs during gameplay caused players to be disconnected, disrupting the session. One main remark focused on the ambiguity around the target audience and intended outcomes of the game, with questions raised about whether it is meant as a university-level educational tool or a training resource for disaster risk management professionals. A summary screen at the end of the game was found to be helpful in facilitating reflections and consolidating learning. Participants also expressed uncertainty about what actions to take and how to navigate the game. In response, the developer implemented pop-up tutorial windows at the start of the game, designed to guide players through the initial stages and ease the onboarding process. Additionally, the varying levels of enthusiasm among players in assuming their roles highlighted the need for a more consistent gameplay dynamic. As a potential solution, some participants suggested introducing a neutral moderator role, namely an external guide tasked with subtly steering the session forward and ensuring balanced participation across the group.

During the second usability testing session, conducted on **Friday, 7 March 2025**, a second set of constructive feedback was gathered to inform future improvements. Participants noted that it still took several rounds to understand the objectives and gameplay mechanics. This time, a supporting manual distributed ahead of the simulation, suggested the inclusion of at least one test round among standard good practices, to allow players to familiarise with the dashboard. Visually, the game was perceived as cluttered and somewhat primitive. Participants suggested that adding topographical features could help create a clearer sense

of movement across a national landscape, rather than appearing confined to a city. However, this idea was ultimately discounted out of fears that introducing additional visual elements might exacerbate the clutter and further complicate the user experience. Concerns about inclusivity were also raised, particularly regarding the male-dominated appearance of role character silhouettes. In terms of gameplay dynamics, participants questioned whether access to all resources by all players might enhance engagement, and whether allowing edits to character bios could introduce more diverse perspectives and decision-making tensions. Additionally, the timing of events within the game was found to be unclear: many actions occurred post-disaster, leading to confusion around anticipatory responses like evacuation. Clarifying the sequence of events, possibly through a chat box message at the beginning of the scenario, was suggested to help orient players more effectively. All these remarks were addressed in a timely fashion to bring the latest version of Bridging the Silos to fruition.

The serious game is now available at: <https://bridging-the-silos.myriadproject.eu/>

Dissemination level of the document

- Public
- Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the European Commission Services)
- Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the European Commission Services)

Version History

Version	Date	Authors/Reviewers	Description
V1	19/05/2025	Authored by Emma Cabascia (Arctik), Gloria Turetta (Arctik), Agnieszka Pietruczuk (Arctik). Reviewed by Philip Ward,	Only to be completed for submissions to reviewers and submissions to the EU portal
V2	04/06/2025		Revised version submitted to Quality Unit
V3	27/06/2025		Version submitted to ECAS

